

**LEVEL OF AWARENESS AND TECHNICAL WRITING SKILLS OF TEACHERS
IN DEVELOPING AN APPLICATION OF EDUCATION PROJECT****Zijen P. Lopez**

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ABSTRACT

Research and development become a primary responsibility of teachers among public schools in the Philippines. By conducting comprehensive researches and innovative works, they are meticulously addressing the surfaced instructional problems, issues and challenges. Part and parcel of such research and innovative work made and to be made by teachers in the public school system was the development of an Application of Education project. This study described and examined public school teachers' level of awareness and technical writing skills in developing and completing an Application of Education project. It employed a descriptive correlational research design which was participated by randomly selected public school teachers in the Philippines. The study found out that teachers were moderately aware in terms of the purpose of the project and they were technically skilled in terms of detail-oriented aspect in developing an Application of Education Project. Results of the study further revealed that when teachers' awareness of their writing purpose increases, their skills in details in developing the project also increases.

Keywords:

Awareness, technical, writing, skills, Application of Education, clarity, detail-oriented

INTRODUCTION

Teachers perform diverse functions in the community, their primary function as teachers encompasses the delivery of quality-based instruction. Teachers are commonly known as the "implementers of curriculum," with their subject expertise through their long-labored study, they are able to design, formulate and utilize effective instructional teaching strategies that develop their learners' competence holistically. In this line, one of the basic aim of the Philippine educational system is to ensure that Filipino learners are accorded with the quality of education which they can use to pursue their career or create employment in the future. Education plays a critical roles in the development of the nation. While teachers are continually exerting their efforts and extend their diligence to ensure that the delivery of quality-based education takes place within the bounds of basic education system in the Philippines, they are also tasked with different work and assignments which are related to their functions as teachers. One of the apparent related tasks which teachers do within the lines of their government service is the continued exploration of pedagogical knowledge through research and development. In fact, the Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines has continually thriving its efforts and maximizing its resources to advance the promotion of research-based pedagogical work among schools in the Philippines. In addition, when the department has strongly emphasized the gravity of researches for continuing professional development as well as pedagogical developments to be made by teachers within their career, technical writing skills and teachers' ability to complete such research work became one of the foremost concern.

Within the basic education system, formulation and completion of classroom-based action researches pervasively navigate teachers' instructional duties as they are encouraged to formulate action researches in order to serve as bases for policy development or at the very least, to provide scientific baseline for further enhancement in any of the dimensions surrounding the instructional system in the basic education institutions.

Hence, as this scholarly work has been embedded among teachers, positioning of a newly implemented scholarly work in the basic education system which teachers ought to administer has been taken place. The imposition of Application of Education. This scholarly work refers to the contribution of teachers that have led to positive outcome in their respective school or workplace as a result of their learnings from higher education earned. In this line, as teachers pursue their higher studies such as master and doctorate degrees respectively, they are to apply significant learnings acquired under their higher studies once they have already completed such. Thus, application of education can simply defined as the application of significant learnings learned by teachers as they completed their master or doctorate degrees. The development of innovative work such researches, programs, interventions and the like are important fibers in the ascertainment that quality of education is desired to be provided among Filipino learners. On one hand, teachers' work autonomy, commitment and diligence have positively impacted the creation of essential conditions encouraging the community to formulate and complete innovative works for the academic community (Baharuddin et al., 2019). Higher degree of exposure to innovations emphasizing teachers' awareness and technical writing skills were significant factors to establish active research and development writing culture among schools (Schmitz et al., 2020). Further, teachers fundamental abilities, desire to continue learning and reflection skills in developing innovative work were essential to build highly impactful research culture in the academic communities (Kunlasomboon et al., 2025). Importance of research and innovation in schools helped teachers to create highly effective programs that addressed classroom-based instructional problems and challenges (Henthorn et al., 2022). Success of schools was also determined by the quality of research and innovative works made. When researches and innovative works were put into consistent practice, high level of instruction could be obtained (Maca, 2019).

Consequently, the researchers observed that most of their colleagues are afraid to formulate an Application of Education projects arising from their confusion and low level of confidence in completing the project. In addition, the researchers observed that most of their colleagues posed lesser interests in writing and administering Application of Education project. In this line, the researchers also found out that there were scarcity on empirical studies that focused on the interplay of level of awareness and technical writing skills of teachers in doing an Application of Education project. Based from the comprehensive readings made by the researchers, they only found out that most of the researches published were purely concentrated on the potential effects of innovative works and researches administered by teachers but failed to scientifically examine the level of awareness and technical writing skills of teachers specially in completing an Application of Education project. In view of these foregoing conditions, this paper described and examined the level of teachers' awareness and technical writing capabilities in doing an Application of Education project among selected public schools in the Philippines. Apparently, this study supported Sustainable Development Goal (SDG-4) Quality of Education. Since this study examined the teachers' awareness in completing an Application of Education project, this was vital to contribute in the attainment of the mentioned sustainable development goal as it may provide scientific baseline for formulating and implanting programs that may help teachers developed their awareness and technical writing skills.

OBJECTIVES

This study described and examined public school teachers' level of awareness and technical writing skills in developing and completing an Application of Education project. Specifically, this study described the level of awareness of teachers in developing an Application of Education project as to clarity, purpose and high regard for ideas and impact of the project. Also, this study described teachers' level of technical writing skills in developing and completing the project in terms of analytical aspect, ability to connect learned concepts to project and detail-oriented. Lastly, the study examined if there would be a significant relationship between teachers' level of awareness and technical writing skills in developing an Application of Education project.

Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers' level of awareness and technical writing skills in developing an Application of Education project.

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METHODOLOGY

Descriptive correlational research was employed so as to describe and examine public school teachers' level of awareness and technical writing skills in developing and completing an Application of Education project. The researchers selected the participation of 150 public school teachers. There were 75 elementary school teachers and 75 junior high school teachers who served as the subject-respondents of the study. Further, the researcher used a researcher-made survey-questionnaire which was validated and subjected to internal consistency measure. Thus, the developed survey-questionnaire contained two (2) parts. For part 1, it contained items relating to teachers' level of awareness in developing an Application of Education project while part 2 contained items relating to teachers' level of technical writing skills in developing the project. Part 1 of the developed instrument utilized a 4-Likert scale such as: 4-Highly Aware, 3-Aware, 2-Not Aware and 1-Highly Not Aware while items under part 2 was rated using a similar scale but employing different verbal descriptions such as: 4-Highly Skilled, 3-Skilled, 2-Moderately Skilled and 1-Not Skilled. Thus, researchers sought the expertise of professionals who validated the developed survey-questionnaire. Apparently, items under the part 1 of the developed survey-questionnaire obtained a Cronbach Alpha result ($\alpha=.971$) while items under part 2 gained a Cronbach Alpha result of ($\alpha=.856$) which were both signified that the items were "Acceptable." The researchers used relevant statistical tools such as mean, standard deviation and general weighted mean in order to describe teachers' level of awareness and technical writing skills in developing an Application of Education project. Meanwhile, Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) was used in order to examine if there would be significant relationship between teachers' level of awareness and technical writing skills in developing an Application of Education project. On one hand, the researchers complied with the highest ethical standards in doing an independent research through administration of short orientations and provision of informed consent among the researchers. In addition, the researchers carefully stored and destroyed the data gathered after the finality of this paper. There were no monetary incentives given nor gifts provided for the respondents. Only an appreciation letters were individually distributed and sent to the respondents as a gesture of gratitude.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research and development becomes a primary responsibility of teachers among public schools in the Philippines. By conducting comprehensive researches and innovative works, they are meticulously addressing the surfaced instructional problems, issues and challenges. Part and parcel of such research and innovative work made and to be made by teachers in the public school system was the development of an Application of Education project. This underscored the conversion of their learned concepts from their higher studies into actionable and highly impactful project. The importance of describing and examining teachers' level of awareness and technical writing skills in developing an Application of Education project would lay basis for the development of program intervention that may help them develop or sustained such skills.

1. **Teachers' Level of Awareness in Developing an Application of Education Project.** The result showed that teachers were moderately aware in terms of purpose ($w_m=1.76$) in developing an Application of Education project. There were moderately aware on the purpose of developing the project. This means that they understood and absorbed the primary intention of the project as a mean for creating a highly impactful innovative work that transfer their acquired learnings from their higher studies into practice and eventually, address instructional gaps, learning loss and challenges they encountered as teachers and curriculum implementers. On one hand, teachers were not aware in developing an Application of Education project in terms of the project's clarity ($w_m=1.56$) and high regard for ideas and impact ($w_m=1.42$). This signified that teachers were not fully aware with the clarity of the project as they expressed confusion on how they would transfer their learned concepts from their higher studies into actionable projects. Also, the findings showed that teachers were not aware on the content of the project's template which also caused their confusion in developing the project. On one hand, teachers were also not aware on the manner by which ideas could be comprehensively presented in the project as the primary aim of the project was to transfer their acquired learnings into a project. Added to this, teachers were also not aware on the creation and development of such project which could emphasize its impact to their functions as teachers. The results revealed that teachers were only moderately aware on the purpose of the project but not aware on the clarity and ideas and impact aspect when developing an Application of Education project. Results supported the study of Naz and Malik (2014) which concluded that teachers were not familiar

with the technical concept and procedure of innovative works and action research development because of unclear understanding to the project's ideation procedure and presentation of its potential impact. Practically, teachers should extend their diligence to personally examine and comprehend the constructs of Application of Education project proposal. On the part of the school heads, consistent and impactful training and workshop should be locally administered in order to enhance teachers' awareness in developing an Application of Education project.

2. **Level of Teachers' Technical Writing Skills in Developing an Application of Education Project.**

The results showed that teachers were skilled in terms of detail-oriented aspect ($w_m=3.42$). This implied that teachers could analyze and examine the conditions confronting their experiences as teachers in public school system. Additionally, the findings showed that teachers were skilled in enumerating every detail where instructional challenges and gaps could be presented on a scholarly work such as an Application of Education project. Further, teachers were skilled in extracting technical aspect of an Application of Education proposal through initial drafting of the project. However, the results showed that teachers were not skilled in terms of analytical ($w_m=1.22$) and ability to learned connect concepts to project ($w_m=1.9$). The results implied that teachers were not skilled in comprehensively examining the core concepts they have learned to be put into the project. They have expressed that their skills were not substantial to develop an Application of Education project because they found that the concepts they have learned may not apparently relevant to the gaps, challenges and issues they have experienced in their respective schools. Further, teachers were not that skilled in comprehensively presenting their strong analysis on the conditions which could substantiate the developed project. In other words, teachers only observed conditions that were obvious and need no further interventions which directly contradicted the purpose and goal of an Application of Education project. Results of the study negated the study of Nayak (2021) which concluded that teachers should focus on the development of their technical writing skills as these could practically helped them address teaching challenges and problems through comprehensive research and other scholarly works. Practically, the study implicated that teachers should extend their efforts to personally learn relevant techniques and approaches in developing their technical writing skills specially in research and innovative works including Application of Education project. Apparently, school heads should also create a program intervention to help their teachers develop their technical writing skills in developing an Application of Education project.

3. **Relationship Between Teachers' Level of Awareness and Technical Writing Skills in Developing an Application of Education Project.**

The result showed that teachers level of awareness in terms of purpose was significantly related to their level of technical writing skills in terms of detail-oriented aspect ($r=.443$). This suggested that as teachers' awareness of their writing purpose increases, their skills in details in developing the project also increases. The results also implied that there was a tendency for teachers who understand their writing purpose could demonstrate stronger detail-oriented skills as core part of technical writing skills in developing an Application of Education project. Results of the study supported the study of Cabudbod et al. (2024) which revealed that effective writing skills were fundamental across various disciplines and careers. Similar study also concluded that content, details, mechanics and grammar were predictors of writing proficiency. Practically, the study implicated that both teachers and school heads administer workshops and training sessions that could enhance their understanding of the purpose relative to the development of an Application of Education project. In addition, teachers and school heads should work hand-in-hand to advance their awareness and technical writing skills in order to develop a highly impactful Application of Education project.

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CONCLUSION

Development of an Application of Education project was one of the primary innovative projects in the Department of Education that advanced the provision of quality instruction leading to the achievement of quality

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education through transferring learned concepts, principles and theories by which teachers learned from higher studies. Their awareness and technical writing skills were significant dimensions to proceed with the development of the project. The found out that teachers were moderately aware in terms of the purpose of the project and they were technically skilled in terms of detail-oriented aspect in developing an Application of Education Project. Conclusively, when teachers' awareness of their writing purpose increases, their skills in details in developing the project also increases.

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